

OPTIMISING FORMING PROCESS BEHAVIOR USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Muhammad. S. Saeed, Ayesha Quddus, Hamas Khan, Hadia Zulfiqar, Boris. Eisenbart, Racim Radjef,
Matthias. Kreimeyer

Motivation and Research Objectives

- Forming process - used to shape flat sheets of material into three-dimensional components
 - Stamp Forming - using a stamping press as in Fig 1
 - Diaphragm Forming - using a diaphragm or flexible membrane
- Artificial Intelligence - to increase the simulation accuracy of forming process
 - Optimisation - to improve simulations and time for computations, while reducing the cost
 - Defect Detection - to overcome defects by detecting them at early stage of design, using point cloud as shown in Fig 2

Fig 1: Stamp Forming

Fig 2: Point Cloud Scanned

Introduction

- Simulation-driven evaluations help in reducing the cost of forming processes by various Artificial Intelligence based optimisation steps as illustrated in Fig 3.
- Several Machine Learning techniques such as Genetic Algorithm are used to predict and classify forming behavior.
- Induced forming defects, such as wrinkles, bridging, voids, are optically inspected using point cloud-based system.

Geometry

A beam model for initial testing

Parameterisation

Parametrise the material parameters such as young's modulus and shear modulus

Genetic Algorithm

Minimise or maximise the parameters to get the optimum results

Analysis

Pareto plots to depict the relationship between different parameters

Fig 3: Process Chain

Initial Evaluations

- Optimisation - Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) is implemented for curve fitting and Multi-objective Genetic Algorithm (GA) for finding optimas. Pareto plots and Open-source tools like Para View and HDF View are used for visualisations of simulations as seen in Fig 4.
- Defect Detection - Defects are detected by analysing the surface normal. The normal vectors for the simulation and point cloud are compared and visualised as in Fig 5.

Fig 4: Beam Visualisations

Fig 5: Cloud Compare

Results and Future Outlook

- The optimisation tool has been deployed for a beam model, now it is being validated on a Double Dome geometry as displayed in Fig 6.
- The scanned points are being removed based on an angle threshold as in Fig 7. Additionally, preprocessing techniques such as Octrees, multithreading, KNNs, and distance threshold are used.

Fig 6: Double Dome Visualisation

Fig 7: Point Cloud Visualisation

Ayesha Quddus
B.Eng. Student – National University of
Science and Technology

Hamas Khan
MSc. Student. – Technical University of
Munich

Hadia Zulfiqar
B.Eng. Student – National University of
Science and Technology

Muhammad Saeed
PhD Candidate – Swinburne University of
Technology & University of Stuttgart
msaeed@swin.edu.au

A/Prof. Dr. Boris Eisenbart
Director of the Testlab
beisenbart@swin.edu.au

Prof. Dr. Matthias Kreimeyer
Head of “Product Development and Design
Technology”
matthias.kreimeyer@iktd.uni-stuttgart.de

Dr. Racim Radjef
Research Engineer
rradjef@swin.edu.au

Thank you

